

TOM RACHEL HUNTER JASON PETER JOSH VIOLA
BLYTH ZEGLER SCHAFFER SCHWARTZMAN DINKLAGE ANDRÉS RIVERA AND DAVIS

THE HUNGER GAMES

THE BALLAD OF

SONGBIRDS & SNAKES

BY SUZANNE COLLINS SCREENPLAY BY MICHAEL LESSLIE AND MICHAEL ARNDT DIRECTED BY FRANCIS LAWRENCE

NOVEMBER 17

LIVEWORKSHEETS